
Ensuring Excellence: Instructional Supervision Practices Of Private Sectarian Secondary School Supervisors

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ABSTRACT

Supervision in education is a multifaceted process aimed at fostering teacher growth, enhancing educational quality, and enriching student learning experiences. Among its various forms, instructional supervision plays a key role by ensuring that schools achieve their vision and mission through the supervision, training, and empowerment of teachers. This study examines the extent to which instructional supervision is implemented in private sectarian secondary schools in La Union. Using a mixed-method approach—surveys and one-on-one interviews—relevant data were collected to assess these supervisory practices. Quantitative data were analyzed using means and categorization scales, while qualitative insights were drawn from thematic analysis. A major outcome of this research is the Tri-phasic Instructional Supervision Model, which outlines how school leaders and department heads implement supervision. This model highlights their commitment to fostering a progressive learning environment and improving teaching performance. The study underscores the value of instructional supervision for school administrators. It suggests implications for policy-making, educational governance, and future research directions.

Keywords: Instructional supervisory practices, intervention, guidance, support, performance assessment

INTRODUCTION

In this dynamic era, where the demand for quality education has never been higher, schools face the imperative to adapt,

innovate, and persevere against all odds. Education serves as a tool to instigate change in human life and lays the foundation for development. Schools actively implement formal education, requiring collaboration among various stakeholders for successful implementation. However, the effectiveness of the educational system and the quality of education primarily depend on school management and leadership. Consequently, educational supervisors play a crucial role in supporting teachers, who act as facilitators in student learning. The achievement of supervision goals hinges on the collaborative efforts of instructional supervisors and teachers, who must be trained, highly motivated, and properly guided by their supervisors.

Supervision in education serves as a guiding compass, supporting educators in navigating pedagogical complexities and upholding ethical standards (Grove, 2019). As educational institutions aim to cultivate twenty-first-century skills in graduates, teacher competence becomes pivotal in achieving these educational goals. The way teachers receive support and supervision from leaders significantly influences the outcomes of the supervision process (Wahyuddin, 2020). Collaborative approaches between educational administrators and teachers are key to enhancing the teaching-learning process and fostering effective education (Solheim et al., 2018). Moreover, teachers' engagement with supervisory practices, including various techniques and models employed by supervisors, serves as the driving force behind successful supervision (Garcia & Weiss, 2019).

One type of supervision in the educational context is instructional supervision. Instructional supervision is a continuous, collaborative process in education focused on enhancing instructional quality. It involves guidance, assistance, and idea-sharing to help teachers improve learning environments (Wahyu, 2020). This type of supervision is highly significant, as administrators can reinforce teaching practices, thereby positively influencing student learning (Oriente & Alvarado, 2020). By skillfully analyzing performance data, administrators can offer meaningful feedback to teachers, profoundly impacting classroom learning. Given that student learning is the core purpose of schools, effective instructional supervision emerges as a critical function for administrators.

Concerning this, David et al. (2021) highlight the importance of instructional supervision, noting that educational supervisors' instructional supervision practices significantly improve teachers' professional competence, making them more effective for learners' benefit. The quality of teaching, which directly influences learners' achievement, hinges on the effectiveness of the department head teachers and the school principal's instructional supervision. It was also highlighted in the study by Ngloe and Mklulu (2020) that effective instructional supervision was found to be the key factor for academic performance in schools and that instructional supervision should be ongoing, focused on teacher support and learners' needs.

However, challenges are likely to arise in any aspect. Effective instructional supervision cannot occur because some supervisors lack time due to busy schedules and heavy workloads, do not prioritize supervision, lack sufficient training and support, or misunderstand the purpose of supervision (McCrickard, 2022). The problems related to instructional supervisory practices always play a key role in the success or failure of an education system (Terra & Berhanu, 2019). A system that is not thoroughly supervised and evaluated will crumble, resulting in poor academic performance, absenteeism, lateness, disrespect toward school authority, low morale, and diverse forms of disruptive behavior (Adikwu et al., 2020).

In Nigeria, ineffective instructional supervisory practices by school heads contribute to teachers' ineffectiveness and low commitment, resulting in subpar instruction (Sule et al., 2018). Similarly, in Ghana, inadequate supervision of lesson preparation by school heads leads to diminished teacher role performance (Ampofo et al., 2019). Conversely, a study by Akib and Mushin (2019) emphasizes the vital role of educational supervisors and teachers' willingness in ensuring educational efficiency. Ineffective instructional supervision in Nigeria correlates with a decline in the overall educational system (Ijaiya, 2019). In Wakisso District, Uganda, inadequate instructional supervision by head teachers in private secondary schools, relying on informal classroom visits rather than structured supervision, contributes to poor teacher performance (Nwankwoala, 2020).

Apart from this, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted regular schooling in the Philippines, leading to various schooling options, from modular to online instruction. School closures resulted in learning gaps among learners, posing challenges for both teachers and students. The Department of Education (DepEd) implemented the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) to enhance learning continuity and recovery. Effective instructional supervision practices aligned with 21st-century student needs are emphasized (Basilio, 2021), highlighting the importance of regular monitoring and supportive supervision for teachers' professional development (Noor et al., 2020). Similarly, there's a call for school administrators to improve the implementation of instructional supervision practices to better support teachers (Sumapal & Haramain, 2023). Overall, effective supervision at all education levels is crucial for the efficient management of teaching and learning processes and ensuring quality education. Supervision should focus on enhancing teachers' competencies and addressing challenges to achieve effective educational outcomes (Michael, 2020).

The Basic Education Act of 2001 (RA 9155) serves as the foundation for instructional supervision. The Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001 establishes a framework for governance in basic education, emphasizing the importance of instructional supervision in both public and private schools. It delineates the jurisdiction and responsibility of educational institutions, including private schools, in delivering high-quality education. This legislation, rooted in national policy, is committed to upholding and promoting every citizen's right to receive a quality basic education. Its objective is to ensure equal access to education for all Filipino children through the provision of free and mandatory education at the elementary level, and free education at the secondary level. Similarly, DepEd Order 42, issued in 2017, acknowledges the pivotal role of teachers in nurturing learners and underscores the importance of competent educators in enhancing academic performance.

Additionally, DepEd Order 25, issued in 2020, highlights the supervisor's crucial function in enhancing the quality of education at regional, divisional, or school levels. Teachers need proper guidance and motivation to seek out new opportunities

to learn. With these, instructional supervisors should act as learning catalysts, teacher motivators, and knowledge sharers through instructional supervision (Department of Education, Republic of the Philippines, 2022).

The City Schools Division of Dasmariñas in Region IV-A, Calabarzon, acted by issuing Division Memorandum No. 253, s. 2022. This memorandum aligns with the DepEd policy and the Learning Recovery Plan. It directs the City Schools Division of Dasmariñas to implement instructional supervision to guide instructional leaders, school principals, master teachers, head teachers, and teachers. The directive mandates that each school's instructional supervision include the development of monthly supervisory plans for teachers and master teachers, as well as an annual supervisory plan for the school principal. The primary objective is to establish a professional, continuous, and collaborative process to enhance instructional quality. Similarly, in Region X-Northern Mindanao's Division of Malaybalay City, Dr. Victoria Gazo, the Assistant Schools Division Superintendent, actively issued Division Memorandum No. 057, s. 2023, on February 23, 2023. This memorandum focuses on the enforcement of instructional supervision through collaborative classroom observation and the utilization of the Rating Sheet for Teachers and Classroom Observation. The primary objective is to facilitate the seamless delivery of teaching and learning instructions across schools and learning centers.

Additionally, this initiative aims to establish a standardized, comprehensive developmental framework to support teachers' professional growth within professional learning communities actively. The overarching goal is to enhance instructional capabilities and, consequently, improve learning outcomes (Department of Education, Division of Malaybalay City, 2023).

In addition, according to Lagado (2023), in Region VIII (Eastern Visayas), the Schools Division Superintendents issued Regional Memorandum No. 133. 2023, containing the updates on the conduct of instructional supervision and implementation of the guide for instructions yielding to archetypal teachers and learning achievements via a mentoring program. The memoran-

dum mandated the supervisors to use the Instructional Supervision Plan and to conduct the supervision every month to enhance the teacher's teaching competency.

Principals face hurdles in fulfilling their supervisory duties, including insufficient preparation for supervision, strained relationships between teachers and supervisors, and inadequate support from higher authorities. Although supervisors may be proficient in their subject matter, they often lack formal qualifications and continuous training to stay abreast of educational advancements crucial for effective supervision. The heavy workload on school supervisors, encompassing administrative duties and personal teaching responsibilities, frequently restricts the time available for practical supervisory tasks within their schools (Enaigbe, 2009; Ngole & Mkulu, 2021).

Conversely, multiple inquiries examine instructional supervisory methods in public and Catholic educational institutions to foster academic distinction (Whelan, 2019; Rufus, 2023). Catholic schools confront various challenges that jeopardize their mission and operational continuity, such as the erosion of values, attrition among educators, and dwindling enrollment figures (Bual & Madrigal, 2018; CEAP, 2016; Madrigal & Oracion, 2019; Caruso, 2012). To tackle these issues, the Philippine Catholic Schools Standards (PCSS) were formulated by CEAP, providing schools with guidance on harmonizing their practices with Church doctrines and international benchmarks (CEAP, 2016; Bual & Madrigal, 2018). These standards are geared towards bolstering the enduring viability and caliber of Catholic education by ensuring alignment with Church precepts (CEAP, 2016; Madrigal & Oracion, 2019).

Furthermore, Bual and Madrigal (2018) underscore how diocesan schools attain exemplary Catholic education by surpassing PCSS benchmarks, adhering to governmental regulations, and upholding their evangelistic mission. Improving instructional supervisory techniques is crucial to aligning school objectives with Church directives. The significance of adept educators and the enhancement of instructional supervision to elevate diocesan schools to distinction underscores the challenges posed by the departure of qualified teachers (Jorilla & Bual, 2021). Similarly,

Aureada (2021) identifies disparities among school administrators in overseeing instructional aspects, noting that despite recognizing the importance of classroom observations, time constraints and competing responsibilities impede consistent implementation.

In this study's setting, the researcher, affiliated with an educational institution, noted that instructional supervisors face time constraints in supervisory tasks. Respondents highlighted the need to keep up with current educational practices, especially in schools lacking clear instructional supervision procedures. Despite the availability of evaluation tools, there's a limited understanding of supervision's purpose, often reducing it to checking attendance and paperwork, which impacts effectiveness due to heavy workloads, including administrative tasks. Additionally, the observation revealed inadequate time for supervision, leading to poor communication between supervisors and teachers, resulting in misunderstandings and misaligned educational goals. Evaluating teacher performance poses challenges, and last-minute summative observations can cause stress due to inadequate preparation time.

Moreover, in the same setting, the researcher conducted an initial survey about the instructional supervision practices of school heads and department heads. The survey results indicate that the majority of school heads in the locale prioritize classroom observations as a primary method of instructional supervision. However, there is a notable lack of consistent feedback provision following these observations. Additionally, respondents express a desire for more professional development opportunities focused on instructional leadership skills. The survey highlights a need for improved communication channels between school heads and teachers regarding instructional expectations and goals. Overall, these findings underscore the importance of targeted support and training initiatives to enhance instructional supervisory practices in the locale.

In the same manner, as a Senior High School teacher and a Doctor of Education student with a profound appreciation for the significance of instructional supervision for both teachers and students, the researcher is actively engaged in the supervi-

sion processes led by educational leaders at their school. Considering these experiences and insights, the study was initiated to examine the instructional supervisory practices employed by school heads and department heads in the research locale. The overarching goal is to facilitate the successful implementation of instructional supervisory practices in schools, thereby contributing to the overall effectiveness and efficiency of educational administrators, management, and teachers.

Furthermore, the researcher identified a notable gap during the literature review, revealing a scarcity of studies focusing on the instructional supervisory practices of department heads and school heads in private sectarian secondary schools. Building on Haramian's (2019) recommendation for a mixed-methods approach to explore supervisors' role in enhancing teachers' commitment to self-improvement, participation in seminars, training, and enrollment in postgraduate studies, this study aims to address this gap and deepen understanding of managing basic education schools.

Additionally, there is a recognized gap concerning the absence of comprehensive instructional supervisory plans tailored specifically for private sectarian secondary schools. Despite the pivotal role of instructional supervision in enhancing teaching quality and student outcomes, there is a lack of structured guidance on how supervisors and teachers in these schools can effectively implement and benefit from instructional supervision practices.

Lastly, the primary goal of this research is to determine the extent of instructional supervision practices of school heads and department heads in terms of guidance, support, and performance assessment. By doing so, the study aims to contribute significantly to existing knowledge in this field, ultimately enhancing the competencies of these educational leaders. The outcomes of this study are anticipated to lay the groundwork for future instructional supervision training programs specifically tailored for school heads and department heads in Catholic Schools within the Diocese of La Union.

METHODOLOGY

Design and Participants

This study used a sequential explanatory mixed-method design to examine instructional supervisory practices of secondary school supervisors. Quantitative data identified patterns, and qualitative data explored reasons for these practices. Participants included 44 supervisors and 318 teachers from Catholic schools in the Diocese of La Union. For interviews, purposive sampling selected 5 supervisors and 5 teachers who had at least 3 years of experience in a supervisory role and were actively involved in instructional supervision.

Instruments

Quantitative data were collected via validated researcher-made questionnaires with a 5-point Likert scale across three dimensions: teacher guidance, support, and performance assessment (20 indicators each). Five experts confirmed content validity, and reliability was established through pilot testing (Cronbach's $\alpha = 0.97-0.98$). Qualitative data were collected using a validated interview guide focusing on the rationale and effects of supervisory practices.

Procedures

Ethical clearance and participant consent were obtained prior to data collection. Questionnaires were distributed and retrieved by the researcher, and interviews were audio-recorded with permission, transcribed, and securely stored. Data processing followed the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using frequency counts, weighted means, and rankings on a 5-point scale (Very Highly Practiced to Not Practiced). Qualitative data underwent thematic analysis using Braun and Clarke's six-step framework, allowing the identification of themes that supported and explained the quantitative findings. Integration of both data strands provided a comprehensive understanding of supervisors' instructional practices.

RESULTS

Table 1

Summary of the Instructional Supervisory Practices of Private Sectarian Secondary School Supervisors

Phases of Instructional Supervision	Weighted Mean	DE
Guidance	4.35	HP
Support	4.39	HP
Performance Assessment	4.29	HP
Overall Mean	4.34	HP

Table 1 provides an overview of the extent to which supervisors in private sectarian secondary schools implement instructional supervisory practices across three phases of instructional supervision. The table shows that school supervisors in private sectarian secondary schools generally engage in instructional supervisory practices across all three phases to a high degree ($M=4.34$), which is interpreted as highly practiced, indicating that supervisors most of the time practice these practices and have a strong level of implementation and adherence.

Consequently, supervisors in private sectarian secondary schools' most practiced phase of instructional supervision is teachers' support ($M=4.39$), described as highly practiced, indicating that supervisors most of the time engage in activities aimed at supporting teachers in their professional development, instructional delivery, and overall effectiveness. This indicates that by prioritizing teacher support, supervisors demonstrate a commitment to nurturing and enhancing educators' skills and capabilities within their schools.

Based on the researcher's data analysis, supervisors consider cultivating a dynamic learning environment as the reason they prioritize providing support to teachers within the framework of instructional supervision. This theme includes enhancing instructional effectiveness, creating a learning culture, and promoting self-efficacy and autonomy. These themes explain why teachers' support was regarded as the most frequently practiced phase of instructional supervision among private sectarian secondary school supervisors. Participant 3 highlighted this concern, stating, "I want to be directly involved with my teachers, particularly in addressing their individual needs. For me, quality

education can only be provided when there is effective supervision.” Participant 5 expressed a similar sentiment, explaining that

From television, laptop, printer, bond paper, and whiteboard marker, everything is provided because I want my teachers to fully prepare themselves when delivering their lessons. I want them to feel comfortable during their lessons as well. I also send them to seminars and workshops that I believe will truly enhance their teaching capabilities. Additionally, I support them in every contest they participate in.

These statements collectively highlight a focus on enhancing teachers' capabilities through professional development opportunities such as seminars and workshops. By investing in their teachers' continuous learning and growth, they seek to equip them with the skills and knowledge needed to deliver quality education.

Conversely, the performance assessment phase is the least practiced among supervisors ($M=4.29$), yet it is described as highly practiced. This means that supervisors most of the time practice performance assessment, but, in contrast to the emphasis on teacher support, the phase of instructional supervision focused on performance assessment receives less attention from supervisors in private sectarian secondary schools. This also indicates that while it is still implemented to some extent, it is not as prioritized or emphasized as other phases of instructional supervision.

In addition, the supervisors consider resource optimization as a factor or reason that imposes limitations on their ability to prioritize and invest in teachers' performance assessment. This theme includes time constraints and high-volume tasks. These themes explain why the teachers' performance assessment was regarded as the least practiced phase in instructional supervision among private sectarian secondary school supervisors. Participant 1 highlighted this concern by stating:

Performance assessment is very important, but it may be practiced less due to time constraints. Due to my administrative tasks, I often cannot observe their classes regularly. Additional-

ly, since I also need to observe other teachers, post-conferences after each

Participant 2 reiterated this viewpoint, explaining:

A school head has a lot of work to do. There are numerous administrative tasks, paperwork to complete, scheduling teachers, emergency meetings, and other urgent matters that need immediate attention. That is why I was not able to observe my teachers' classes as often as I would have liked.

In the same manner, Participant 4 expressed a similar sentiment, explaining, "I was not able to enter and observe their classes regularly or even visit their classes often because of my busy schedule." These statements collectively highlight the challenges supervisors encounter in effectively implementing the performance assessment phase of instructional supervision.

Additionally, secondary school supervisors highly practice guidance in supervising teachers (M=4.35). This means that private sectarian secondary school supervisors most often practice the teachers' guidance phase of instructional supervision when supervising their teachers. This indicates that supervisors use teachers' guidance when aiming to improve teaching effectiveness and promote student success.

Moreover, supervisors encourage and foster a culture of collaboration among teachers by facilitating PLCs (Professional Learning Communities) or other collaborative structures (M=4.63), which is described as very highly practiced. This practice, under the teachers' guidance phase, means that supervisors encourage a collaborative learning community among the teachers at all times. They aim to enhance teaching effectiveness and improve student learning outcomes, and to enable teachers to come together to discuss teaching strategies, share resources, and reflect on their practices.

Furthermore, the strategies for conducting PLCs (Professional Learning Communities) emerged with one (1) theme and two (2) sub-themes from the analysis of responses from school heads and department heads. Teachers' feedback corroborates the information provided by supervisors, confirming the effectiveness of the identified strategies. In terms of

methodology, the data from both groups of participants underwent distinct analyses before being compared to identify the final themes on the strategies supervisors used to conduct PLCs. Based on the treated data, supervisors conduct PLCs through structural assistance and resources in which the supervisors employ (1) professional sharing, and (2) promoting collaboration. This theme demonstrates the significance of PLCs as a vehicle for guiding teachers' professional growth and fostering a collaborative learning environment that benefits both teachers and students alike.

Supervisors conduct PLCs through structural assistance and resources, specifically by professional sharing. This theme encompasses the provision of structural support and resources by school heads to facilitate PLCs. It includes allocating time in the school schedule for PLC meetings. Participant 1 explained, "Whenever there is a teacher who attended seminars, we gather the teachers for professional learning and sharing. The teachers who attended the seminar shared their learning with the faculty." Participant 6 stated this sentiment, noting, "We conduct PLCs every week for us to plan our Lesson Plan, who will make it, what lessons are to be included, what strategies, and what activities must we give." Participant 9 echoed this concern, explaining, "Our school conducts PLC every week, and every time we need to do professional sharing when a teacher comes back from a seminar or workshop in which he/she will share his/her learning with us. In certain situations, PLC meetings may occur at our school on a quarterly or periodic basis. However, most of the time we do PLC weekly meetings."

These statements emphasize that there is a structured agenda set by school heads, focusing on lesson planning, allocation of responsibilities, inclusion of appropriate teaching strategies, and selection of relevant activities, with flexibility to adjust the frequency based on specific needs or circumstances.

Another strategy used by supervisors in conducting PLCs through structural assistance and resources is promoting collaboration. This theme emphasizes that PLCs improve students' learning experience, particularly through the development of high-quality lesson plans and assessments. In line with this, Par-

Participant 2 mentioned, “We do it frequently as much as possible, especially in crafting lesson plans to give a better learning experience for our students.” Similarly, Participant 4 shared, “We do PLCs by letting the teachers who teach the same subject in the department meet with each other and plan together the LPs, summative test, and even Performance tasks”. Likewise, Participant 6 explained, “...we maximize the time for us to do professional sharing not just on our expertise but also with the challenges we encounter, not just with the lessons but also in dealing with our students.” These statements underscore the commitment to promoting collaboration within PLCs by emphasizing regular engagement, subject-specific planning, and effective utilization of meeting time for sharing knowledge, expertise, and experiences. These emphasize that supervisors encourage a culture of open communication and collaboration within PLCs, where teachers feel comfortable sharing their experiences and supporting one another in addressing common challenges.

Conversely, assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi to determine strategies that best work in the teaching and learning process, and to outline specific strategies and timelines for achieving their goals, has the lowest mean ($M=4.17$), indicating it is highly practiced in instructional supervision. This means that, on average, supervisors are slightly less involved in this indicator than others, and they give slightly less emphasis or attention to assisting teachers in developing their action plans.

On the other hand, time management workload is the reason why assisting teachers in crafting their lesson plans and syllabi to determine strategies that best work in the teaching and learning process, and to outline specific strategies and timelines for achieving their goals, is the lowest indicator in the teachers’ guidance phase. Time management workload refers to the challenges school heads face in balancing their time and workload while providing adequate support to teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi. This includes sustainability and follow-through, as well as differing needs and priorities.

Sustainability and follow-through refer to the context of assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans, ensuring that the support provided is ongoing and not a one-time occurrence. It in-

volves the difficulty of implementing strategies or systems that consistently enable teachers to develop high-quality lesson plans over the long term. Moreover, it involves carrying out actions or commitments to completion. It refers to the challenge of ensuring that teachers implement the lesson plans they have crafted effectively in the classroom. Participant 1's response can explain this: "I find it hard to align the lesson plans and syllabi with the specific needs and goals of the teachers and their students, especially since we have different students per school year."

Participant 2 explained:

I find it hard to ensure that the syllabi and lesson plans are realistic and achievable within the constraints of time, resources, and institutional policies, since a school year can bring a lot of changes; thus, we as educators need to be flexible.

These statements underscore the complexity of lesson planning and syllabus development in education, emphasizing the need for educators to be adaptable, resourceful, and responsive to the dynamic nature of teaching and learning environments.

Moreover, differing needs and priorities are among the challenges school heads face in assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi. This challenge arises because teachers have distinct teaching styles, educational philosophies, and classroom dynamics, leading to differing preferences and approaches in lesson planning. Additionally, students within each classroom may have diverse learning needs, interests, and abilities, requiring customized instructional strategies and content delivery methods. This is explained in Participant 3's response, which mentions, "In providing ongoing support and feedback to teachers as they implement their action plans, since I also have other administrative tasks." Participant 5:

I find it hard to supervise them in crafting lesson plans due to a lack of time. Because of heavy workloads, it is hard for me to assist teachers in crafting their action plans, especially since we follow a PEAC format.

These statements suggest that the school heads find it

challenging to offer ongoing support and feedback to teachers due to competing demands from other administrative tasks. This indicates a struggle to balance administrative responsibilities with the need to support teachers in their professional development and implementation of action plans. Moreover, these statements highlight the difficulty in supervising teachers in crafting lesson plans due to time constraints. The administrator expresses that heavy workloads make it challenging to assist teachers in creating their action plans, particularly when there is a specific format or framework to follow.

Furthermore, supervisors report high levels of support in their instructional supervision in their schools ($M=4.39$). This means that private sectarian secondary school supervisors most of the time practice the teachers' support phase of instructional supervision.

Listening and responding to teachers' concerns ($M=4.57$) is described as very highly practiced. This means supervisors are good at listening to teachers and helping them with their problems. This can make teachers feel more confident and better about themselves when they're teaching. This shows that school supervisors are doing their best to inspire and motivate teachers and are also sharing new ways to teach by talking with them. When they listen to and respond to teachers' concerns, it shows they're there to help and make the school a good place for teaching and learning. Supervisors prioritize recognizing and appreciating the hard work and achievements of teachers, actively acknowledging the valuable contributions they make to the school community.

Furthermore, the strategies employed by teachers during the teachers' support phase of instructional supervision emerged as one (1) theme with three (3) sub-themes, as identified from the analysis of responses from school heads and department heads. Teachers' feedback corroborates the information provided by supervisors, confirming the effectiveness of the identified strategies. In terms of methodology, the data from both groups of participants underwent distinct analyses before being compared to identify the final themes regarding the strategies for employing teachers' support used by the supervisors. Based on

the treated data, supervisors employ teachers' support through the timely provision of resources, specifically (1) recognition of expertise and contribution, (2) transparent communication channels, and (3) professional growth. This theme encompasses various ways in which school heads employ the teachers' support phase in instructional supervision.

Supervisors empower teachers' support by recognizing expertise and contributions. This theme encompasses acknowledging and valuing individuals' knowledge, skills, and contributions within a particular context or domain. Participant 1 explained, "I provide them personalized feedback on their contributions." Participant 3 echoed this concern, stating, "I organize special events or ceremonies to celebrate the teachers' achievements for me to show my appreciation." Participant 5 shared this sentiment, explaining, "I congratulate them personally for their achievements and accomplishments."

These statements were also supported by the teachers' responses when asked about the ways their school head supports teachers. Participant 7 shared that, "The school head shows appreciation for our accomplishments by planning and celebrating a simple yet memorable celebration for all of us." Participant 8, "The school head recognizes our achievements and efforts, and he also sees to it that we have the office supplies needed for our teaching instruction." These statements emphasize the importance of recognizing and honoring individuals' unique talents, perspectives, and efforts, fostering a culture of respect, appreciation, and empowerment. It involves acknowledging individuals' expertise based on their qualifications, experience, and achievements, as well as recognizing their contributions to the success, growth, or advancement of a team, organization, or community.

Another strategy used by supervisors to support teachers is the use of transparent communication channels. This refers to establishing clear and open lines of communication between school supervisors and teachers. This theme emphasizes the importance of creating an environment where information flows freely, feedback is welcome, and concerns are addressed openly and honestly. Transparent communication channels enable

teachers to express their thoughts, share ideas, seek assistance, and provide feedback on various aspects of their professional development and teaching practices. This is evident in Participant 1's response, who echoed this sentiment, explaining, "I encourage open communication with my teachers in which I listen to my teachers' concerns." Participant 4 mentioned, "What I do is to listen to their concerns and if I can, try to respond and address their concerns." Participant 5 explained, "I also serve as their surfboard every time they have some personal problems, kasi I can be their ate or mother naman sa school e." These statements suggest that the school supervisors prioritize open communication and support for their teachers' well-being and professional growth. Also, the statements indicate that supervisors value teachers' input and perspectives, creating an environment where teachers feel comfortable expressing their thoughts, ideas, and challenges. They commit to supporting teachers and ensuring that their needs are heard and addressed promptly. These statements further underscore that the supervisors see themselves not only as professional mentors but also as sources of personal support.

In addition, another strategy supervisors employ during the teachers' support phase is offering professional development opportunities. This theme refers to the ongoing development and improvement of teachers' knowledge, skills, and competencies related to their profession. This theme encompasses various activities, opportunities, and resources provided to teachers to enhance their effectiveness as educators and promote their continuous learning and development. This is evident in Participant 2's response: "What I do is I am encouraging them, supporting them to enroll and finish their post-graduate studies, recommending them to attend seminars and training for them to hasten their skills and abilities, especially the teachers who coach students during contests." Participant 3 also shared this concern, explaining, "I see to it that there is a fair and equal chance for them to be selected as participants during seminars and webinars." Participant 4 mentioned, "I am sending my teachers to seminars and encouraging collaboration and teamwork for the teachers to work cooperatively to complete most of the paperwork." These statements imply that supervisors should ac-

tively foster, support, and sustain a culture of professional growth within the school, recognizing that such efforts can enhance teacher effectiveness and ultimately lead to better educational outcomes for students.

Meanwhile, supervisors employ teachers' support for Quality Education. This theme focuses on why school supervisors support their teachers' professional development and career growth to ensure quality education. This includes building teacher capacity, improving student learning outcomes, and recognizing impact. Additionally, the reasons why supervisors employ the teachers' support phase of instructional supervision emerged as one (1) theme with three (3) sub-themes from the analysis of responses from school heads and department heads. Based on the treated data, supervisors employ teachers' support for Quality Education specifically (1) building teacher capacity, (2) student learning outcomes, and (3) recognition of impact. This theme encompasses various reasons why school heads employ the teachers' support phase in instructional supervision.

Supervisors employ the teachers' support phase of instruction to build teacher capacity. This refers to the process of developing and enhancing teachers' knowledge, skills, and abilities to improve their instructional practice and positively impact student learning. This implies that when school supervisors focus on building teacher capacity, they are taking an active role in both their teachers' personal and professional development. This is evident in the response of Participant 1, stating, "I believe that's the right thing to do. They deserve to be praised, they also deserve to be taken care of, and at the same time, they deserve to be thanked." Participant 2 mentioned, "By providing guidance, feedback, and resources, I can also assist teachers in improving their instructional practices, refining their pedagogical techniques, and staying current with educational trends as well." Participant 5 shared the same sentiment, stating, "This improves teaching effectiveness, enhances student learning outcomes, and fosters a positive school culture." These statements highlight that supervisors are important facilitators in a cycle of continuous improvement for teachers, with the end goal of optimizing the educational experience for students and fostering a dynamic, positive school community.

Another reason supervisors employ the teachers' support phase is to improve student learning outcomes. By supporting teachers, supervisors can help them develop more effective teaching methods, which directly impact students' ability to learn and succeed academically. This further indicates that supervisors support and encourage the adoption of proven instructional strategies, which can lead to greater student engagement and a better understanding of the material. This is evident in Participant 2's response: "I want them to be the best they can be because they have a significant impact on students' performance." Participant 3 shared, "So that I can also ensure that quality education is truly delivered to the children." Participant 5 mentioned, "I want to ensure that teachers do their job properly, encouraging us to enroll in our post-graduate studies." These statements suggest that it's the job of supervisors to ensure the education provided is high-quality and keeps improving. Supervisors must monitor teachers' progress and help them develop their skills over time.

In addition, another reason why supervisors employ the teachers' support phase is the recognition of its impact. This refers to the various ways in which supervisors show their gratitude to the teachers. This means recognizing the impact involves understanding and supporting effective teaching methods that improve student learning. It shows that when supervisors acknowledge and support teachers' growth, both teacher performance and student success can be boosted. Supervisors are aware that their role is crucial to improving how well classes are taught, and they aim to ensure their support leads to real changes in the classroom. They use evidence of what works in teaching to make smart choices for future training and resources for teachers. This is evident in Participant 2's response: "It's our way to express our gratitude for their pivotal role in molding young minds and paving the way for the next generation." Participant 3 stated, "For me, it's a way of expressing gratitude for their tireless efforts to inspire, educate, and support our students." Participant 4 mentioned, "Recognition motivates teachers to strive for excellence." The statements highlight the supervisor's role in the teachers' support phase of instructional supervision as one that not only acknowledges the importance of

teachers' contributions but also actively seeks to celebrate and reinforce them through various forms of appreciation. This, in turn, can lead to a more motivated and effective teaching staff, contributing positively to the whole educational process. Also, recognizing the impact means holding everyone involved accountable for students' learning. When supervisors' and teachers' efforts are recognized and valued, it creates an environment where teachers feel confident to try new things and be innovative, all to help students learn better.

On the other hand, supervisors highly practice working closely with teachers to identify areas of their teaching practice that could benefit from improvement ($M=4.19$). This means that although most of the time they employ this practice in supervising their teachers, not all the time do supervisors work closely with teachers to collaborate and pinpoint areas of their teaching practice that could be enhanced.

Supervisors cited workload pressures as the reason this indicator was ranked lowest. This refers to the demands and responsibilities placed on individuals within a certain role or profession that consume their time and energy. These pressures can arise from various sources, such as high task volume, tight deadlines, administrative duties, meetings, or productivity expectations. Workload pressures can lead to stress, overwhelm, and difficulty managing one's workload effectively. This theme includes limited observational procedures, scheduling constraints, and resistance to feedback.

Supervisors attribute this low rating to limited opportunities for them to observe teachers in action. Because they have fewer chances to observe teaching practices directly, supervisors find it challenging to identify and address specific areas where teachers could enhance their effectiveness. In essence, these highlight a gap in the support provided to teachers, particularly in personalized feedback and guidance to improve their teaching practice. This refers to heavy workloads impeding supervisors' ability to dedicate time to this task. In essence, the challenge lies in balancing administrative duties with providing personalized support to teachers. This can be explained by the statement of Participant 1, who said, "There's a lack of time to visit my teach-

ers in their classrooms frequently.” Participant 2, “I find it difficult to find time for observations, feedback sessions, and professional development.” These statements imply that participants are struggling to allocate sufficient time to key aspects of their roles as educators or supervisors.

Moreover, scheduling constraints are among the challenges that school heads and department heads face in this indicator. This refers to limitations or restrictions that affect the ability to allocate time for specific activities within a given timeframe. These constraints can include limited time slots, conflicting priorities, deadlines, or logistical challenges that make it difficult to organize or schedule activities effectively. Scheduling constraints can pose challenges in planning and coordinating tasks, events, or appointments within the available time and resources. Participant 2's statement can explain the finding: “I am not able to work closely with teachers to identify their needs for improvement because of teachers' demanding schedules.” Participant 5 mentioned, “It is difficult because I have a heavy workload and other priorities and responsibilities of a school head.” These statements suggest that participants are facing challenges in providing support to teachers due to various constraints. These highlight the impact of time constraints and competing priorities on educators' ability to provide effective support and guidance to their colleagues.

Furthermore, supervisors regarded the practice of performance assessment as highly practiced ($M=4.29$). Private sectarian secondary school supervisors frequently practice assessments to work collaboratively with teachers to set goals, monitor progress, and adjust instructional strategies as needed to enhance teaching effectiveness and student achievement.

Ensuring that teachers' classroom priorities are consistent with the school's goals and directions ($M=4.41$) is described as highly practiced. This finding indicates that school supervisors strongly urge teachers to ensure that what they do in their classrooms aligns with the school's overall aims. When teachers align their priorities with the school's goals, they become more effective teachers, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes for students. This further underscores the importance of collaboration

and alignment between teachers and the school's broader objectives in fostering student success.

On the other hand, supervisors consider alignment with educational standards as a manner in which they employ the teachers' performance assessment phase of instructional supervision. This theme highlights the strategies school supervisors use in teachers' performance assessments. This includes (1) optimizing the frequency of classroom observations, (2) employing cross-school collaboration, and (3) encouraging collaborative feedback. These themes reflect a structured approach to classroom observation aimed at evaluating teachers' adherence to educational standards and facilitating effective communication of performance expectations to support professional growth and development.

Consequently, optimizing the frequency of classroom observation involves determining the most effective and efficient schedule for conducting them. This theme involves verifying that teachers' content aligns with the prescribed curriculum standards. Moreover, this means supervisors need to assess the effectiveness of teachers' chosen teaching methodologies in facilitating student learning, including observing classroom instruction to determine whether teachers are employing strategies appropriate to the subject matter and conducive to student engagement and understanding. This is evident in Participant 1's response: "I do supervision twice a year, but if I can see that there's still some aspect that the teacher needs to improve, I add additional classroom observation." Participant 2 mentioned, "I observe teachers twice a year, one announced and one unannounced, and these two observations are both graded." Participant 3 echoed, "I observe my teachers during their classroom instruction. I also do it twice a year, announced and unannounced. But as a routine, I roam around the campus every morning to see if the teachers are implementing what is included in their LPs." Participant 4 shared, "Only the newbie teachers undergo pop-in observations by their department heads and by me as the school head. However, all teachers are observed during summative evaluation or summative observation." These statements indicate that supervisors need to ensure teachers' performance aligns with established educational standards,

thereby contributing to high-quality education and student success. This further underscores that supervisors evaluate how teachers assess student learning to ensure that assessment practices are fair, reliable, and aligned with educational standards. They track educational outcomes to gauge the effectiveness of teachers' instruction in achieving desired learning goals. This implies that supervisors play a crucial role in promoting a culture of continuous improvement among teachers by fostering reflection, collaboration, and professional growth.

Cross-school collaboration is also a strategy used by supervisors during the teachers' performance assessment phase of instructional supervision. This theme involves initiatives such as joint professional development, collaborative projects, and the sharing of instructional materials and strategies among schools. Participant 3 shared this sentiment, explaining, "We have our AST observation twice per school year in which principals from other schools go to a certain school and observe the teachers during their classroom instruction." Similarly, Participant 4 also stated, "...the Diocesan schools also have what they call AST observation, in which the principals from the diocesan schools go to a certain school to observe the teachers in their classroom instruction. This is done twice a year, and it is also announced and unannounced." These statements underscore the value of supervisors leveraging collective knowledge and experiences to improve instructional supervision outcomes and support the professional growth of educators across multiple schools or educational settings.

Additionally, supervisors also practice encouraging collaborative feedback in the teachers' performance assessment phase of instructional supervision. This refers to the diversity of viewpoints and insights, which enriches the feedback process and can lead to more comprehensive and balanced evaluations. In line with this, Participant 3 shared this practice, stating, "The teachers also have their peer observations in which the observing teacher visits the classroom of their peer during a scheduled class period." Participant 5 also stated, "They have peer observation. Peer observations are like, you know, part of an ongoing process of professional growth, and teachers need to keep collaborating, sharing feedback, and learning from each other to

improve their practice.” Participant 3 shared this sentiment, stating, “He/she is well-informed about his/her strengths and weaknesses”. He also added, “I give my advice and share my methods or strategies, which I think would be applicable in some instances.” These indicate that supervisors offer constructive feedback, share observations, and collaboratively explore solutions to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. These statements indicate that supervisors solicit input and perspectives from multiple individuals, rather than relying solely on individual assessments or opinions. Conversely, pointing out specific strengths in teachers' instructional practices in post-observation feedback (M=4.04) is interpreted as highly practiced. Despite its lower rating, this finding emphasizes that school supervisors still see strengths in how teachers teach, especially when they give feedback after observing classes. This feedback lets principals check how well their advice is working. This feedback aims to help teachers grow, solve problems, and improve their teaching. The results show that supervisors are recognizing teachers' strengths and offering guidance to improve teaching and learning. By addressing any weak points during evaluations, teaching, and learning can get even better. It's important for supervisors to accurately see how well each teacher is doing and have a way to keep improving things regularly.

While implementing strategies to enhance supervisors' instructional supervisory practices, it's crucial to recognize that challenges may persist despite their best efforts. Even with proactive measures in place, supervisors remain mindful of the inherent complexities and uncertainties that accompany their endeavors. Based on the treated data, supervisors consider striking a balance to be the challenge they have encountered in helping teachers design their lesson plans. This theme highlights the challenges school heads face in implementing teacher performance assessment. It emphasizes the delicate balance supervisors must navigate in managing time constraints to facilitate effective collaboration with teachers. This theme includes (1) Streamlined Observation Procedures, (2) time constraints, (3) communication barriers, and (4) heavy workloads.

Streamlining Observation Procedures in a way that balances accountability and support is one of the challenges super-

visors encounter when assisting teachers in crafting their lesson plans. This theme suggests that streamlined observation procedures during the teachers' performance assessment phase can pose challenges for ensuring comprehensive, nuanced evaluations of teaching effectiveness. While streamlining aims to simplify the process, it may inadvertently overlook important aspects of teaching practice that require deeper analysis. Additionally, there's a risk of reducing observation criteria to a limited set of metrics, potentially neglecting the complexity of classroom dynamics and individual teaching styles. Participant 1 shared this sentiment, explaining, "Not being able to have pre-observation conferences, so I just provide the evaluation tool." The response of Participant 1, a school head, was corroborated by Participant 10, who stated, "Not given an evaluation tool, and we do not know the key areas to be observed." These statements underscore that streamlining procedures may pressure prioritizing efficiency over quality, leading to rushed assessments and superficial feedback. This further indicates that supervisors need to establish clear criteria and expectations for streamlined observations, balancing efficiency with thorough evaluation. Additionally, this offers supervisors an opportunity to enhance the overall quality and impact of teacher performance assessments, contributing to ongoing improvements in teaching and learning outcomes within the school community.

Time constraints are one of the challenges supervisors face when implementing the performance assessment phase. This refers to the limited amount of time available to meet and discuss the upcoming observation. This theme acknowledges that both the supervisor and the teacher being observed have busy schedules, and therefore may make it difficult to find a suitable time to meet before the observation. This concern was shared by Participant 1, who stated, "Aligning the schedules of both the teacher and myself amidst our busy schedules because teachers often have packed agendas with teaching responsibilities, meetings, and other commitments." Similarly, Participant 3 also states, "Difficulty in aligning my schedule with the schedule of the teachers." Participant 5 mentioned, "Time constraints and alignment of my schedule with the teachers' schedule." These statements underscore that limited time may limit the frequency

and duration of observations, thereby reducing supervisors' opportunities to evaluate teachers' instructional practices comprehensively. This also implies that time constraints can hinder supervisors' ability to engage in meaningful follow-up discussions and support teachers in implementing recommended improvements. As a result, supervisors must carefully prioritize their time and resources, balancing efficiency with the need to provide valuable feedback and support to teachers.

Besides, supervisors also consider communication barriers a challenge. This theme refers to the challenges supervisors encounter in effectively employing the teachers' performance assessment phase in instructional supervision. This concern was shared by Participant 1, stating, "As a school administrator, my schedule can also be demanding, with administrative tasks, meetings, and other duties vying for my time." Similarly, Participant 4 explained, "There are conflicting commitments such as teaching duties, meetings, and other responsibilities that may make scheduling difficult." These responses from the school supervisors were corroborated by the responses of the teachers, in which Participant 6 mentioned, "Short notice of last-minute changes due to unforeseen circumstances, such as student emergencies, school events, or meetings, or professional development sessions." Similarly, Participant 9 explained, "When there is an emergency meeting, sudden errands, or tasks to be done, especially when the teacher's schedule is already fully occupied, our principal may need to attend to them." Participant 10, "Communication challenges, such as miscommunication or difficulty reaching the teacher or observer, can hinder the scheduling process." These underscore the need for school supervisors to manage complex scheduling demands, unexpected events, and communication challenges to coordinate performance assessments effectively. Lastly, supervisors also consider heavy workloads as one of the challenges encountered during the teachers' performance assessment phase, making it the least practiced phase in instructional supervision. This theme suggests that heavy workloads can make it difficult for supervisors to allocate sufficient time and attention to prepare for teachers' performance assessments adequately. It may also impact their ability to provide timely and comprehensive feedback to teachers after

the observation. This sentiment was shared by Participant 2, explaining, “Time constraints due to the heavy workloads of teachers.” Participant 3 also shared his sentiment, stating, “Difficulty in aligning my schedule with the schedule of the teachers.” Participant 5 also shared that, “Competing priorities and responsibilities, such as administrative duties, employee supervision, and curriculum development, can impact my availability for scheduling pre-observation conferences on time.”

This theme indicates the significant amount of work or responsibilities that supervisors or observers have, which can present challenges in effectively preparing for and conducting these conferences.

Based on the provided results and findings, this study revealed that the three phases of instructional supervision were predominantly used, with performance assessment being the least used and teachers’ support the most.

Figure 2

Viloria’s Triphasic Model of Instructional Supervision

The presented findings served as a basis for crafting the framework for instructional supervisory practices of school supervisors in private sectarian secondary schools.

Viloria's Triphasic Framework of Instructional Supervision represents a meticulous examination of the complex processes

involved in overseeing and improving teaching practices within educational contexts. Named after the researcher Vilorio, this model encapsulates the essence of instructional supervision, a cornerstone of educational leadership. The term "Triphasic" signifies the framework's division into three distinct phases, each serving a unique purpose in enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes.

Instructional Supervision Strategies are the central focus of the model, embodying the overarching goal of promoting excellence in teaching. It has a blue background because it represents the trust, clarity, and structured guidance inherent in the supervision process. School Heads and Department heads tasked with overseeing instructional practices engage in a triphasic approach encompassing "Guidance," "Support," and "Performance Assessment." Though distinct, these phases collectively contribute to educators' holistic development and to improved teaching quality.

One of the three phases of instructional supervision is the school heads' "guidance" for teachers, shown in green. The green background under this phase represents beginnings, growth, development, and planning because this is the first phase of instructional supervision. This phase is tailored to each teacher's individual needs and goals to enhance teaching effectiveness and promote student success. This phase establishes tight collaboration between instructional leaders and teachers, fostering a professional learning community. School and department heads' "guidance" for teachers is delivered through structural responses. School and department heads guide by fostering professional learning communities through professional sharing and promoting collaboration. The strategies underscore a structured agenda led by school heads, focusing on lesson planning, assigning responsibilities, employing suitable teaching strategies, and selecting relevant activities. This structure allows for flexibility in adjusting meeting frequency based on specific needs or circumstances. Moreover, commitment to fostering collaboration within Professional Learning Communities (PLCs). This commitment emphasizes regular engagement, subject-specific planning, and efficient use of meeting time for sharing knowledge, expertise, and experiences. Supervisors (school heads and department

heads) play a pivotal role in encouraging open communication and collaboration within PLCs, creating an environment where teachers feel at ease sharing experiences and supporting one another in addressing common challenges.

Moreover, during the quantitative phase of the study, the emergence of school heads' "Support" for teachers as the most practiced instructional supervision practice, with a red background. The red background symbolizes the developmental and supportive aspects of instructional supervision, focusing on teachers' and students' continuous improvement and growth. This phase underscores supervisors' proactive stance in bolstering teacher capacity. This emphasis reflects a commitment to providing comprehensive assistance and resources to nurture teachers' professional development and enhance instructional effectiveness. Within this phase, supervisors employ diverse strategies tailored to facilitate teachers' growth and success in the classroom.

One strategy that highlights the importance of offering support is the timely provision of resources tailored to teachers' needs. This underscores the importance of ensuring educators have access to the necessary tools, guidance, and assistance precisely when needed, thereby optimizing their ability to deliver high-quality instruction. School Heads and Department Heads aim to equip teachers with the resources and support they need to navigate challenges and excel in their roles by prioritizing timely support.

Moreover, supervisors implement specific strategies to foster effective communication, recognition, and professional growth among teachers. Transparent Communication Channels serve as a cornerstone, emphasizing the establishment of open, honest, and clear lines of communication between supervisors and teachers. This approach promotes collaboration, feedback exchange, and the sharing of insights, ultimately enhancing instructional practices and fostering a culture of continuous improvement.

Furthermore, the recognition of expertise and contributions is one of the strategies implemented by school heads, underscoring the importance of acknowledging and valuing teach-

ers' knowledge, skills, and contributions within the educational context. By celebrating educators' achievements and expertise, supervisors cultivate a culture of appreciation and empowerment, motivating teachers to strive for excellence and take ownership of their professional development.

Additionally, Professional Development Opportunities represent a key strategy, offering teachers avenues for ongoing learning and growth. These opportunities encompass various training, workshops, and collaborative initiatives designed to enhance teachers' instructional effectiveness and expand their pedagogical repertoire. School Heads and Department Heads empower teachers to stay abreast of emerging trends by investing in professional development, refining their practices, and ultimately optimizing student learning outcomes.

Conversely, "School Heads' Performance Assessment for Teachers" emerges as the least practiced phase, having a purple background, presenting supervisors with challenges related to observation procedures, time constraints, and heavy workloads. Purple serves as a visual cue to draw attention, emphasize its importance, and encourage school supervisors to engage more deeply with this critical component of instructional supervision. One strategy school heads use is to align everything with educational standards, underscoring the importance of ensuring assessments align with established criteria and goals, fostering consistency and effectiveness in evaluation practices.

Within the Alignment with Educational Standards, several specific strategies employed by school heads and department heads were used to enhance performance assessment. Optimizing the Frequency of Classroom Observation emphasizes the importance of regular, comprehensive observations to gauge teaching effectiveness and support professional growth accurately. School and department heads can provide timely feedback and guidance to teachers by conducting frequent observations and facilitating their ongoing development.

Moving along, cross-school Collaboration highlights the collaborative efforts of school and department heads from different schools to exchange insights and resources, enriching the assessment process and fostering consistency in standards

across educational institutions. Through collaborative endeavors, supervisors can leverage collective expertise and experiences to enhance the quality and reliability of performance assessments.

Progressing further, encouraging collaborative feedback underscores the significance of soliciting input from various stakeholders to enrich the feedback process and promote continuous improvement in teaching practices. By embracing collaborative feedback mechanisms, supervisors can gather diverse perspectives and insights, leading to more comprehensive and constructive teacher performance assessments.

The implications of this framework extend beyond research to practical application in educational settings. By emphasizing timely support and comprehensive assessment, supervisors can cultivate a dynamic learning environment and optimize resource allocation. Cultivating a Learning Dynamic Environment and Resource Optimization Opportunity has an orange background because it is known to stimulate mental enhancement and communication, which is believed to be achieved when school heads properly implement instructional supervision. It also symbolizes the motivating and energizing role of instructional supervision, aiming to inspire and uplift educators in their professional journey. Furthermore, the model underscores the importance of effective and efficient teaching performance by teachers with a gold background.

Gold background symbolizes high achievement, excellence, quality, and success, making it a fitting color to represent the pinnacle of teaching performance. With a gold background, school heads and department heads not only celebrate and acknowledge teachers' hard work and success but also create an aspirational standard that others can strive to achieve. As educational leaders navigate the complexities of instructional supervision, this model is valuable for promoting teacher growth and fostering a culture of excellence within schools and educational institutions.

DISCUSSION

This study aimed to determine the extent to which supervisors in the private sectarian secondary schools of La Union implement the three instructional supervisory phases. Supervisors typically use a diverse range of instructional supervision methods, reflecting a wide array of strategies for supervising their teachers during classroom instruction. Supervisors implement the three phases of instructional supervision to varying degrees within their organizations, demonstrating their active involvement in overseeing teachers and their flexibility in using effective methods. The results indicated that school heads regularly engaged in instructional supervision practices, particularly in teacher guidance, support, and performance assessment, yet these practices were not fully implemented.

Moreover, it suggests that supervisors consider adapting the diverse instructional supervisory practices required for effective supervision accordingly. The results also indicated that supervisors encountered several challenges during their supervisory duties, which hindered their supervision. Moreover, this finding underscores their adherence to the guidelines outlined in RA 9155, PPSH, DO 42, S2017, and DO 25, S2020, striving for supervisors to play a pivotal role in enhancing the quality of education at the regional, divisional, or school levels, in which supervisors should act as learning catalysts, teacher motivators, and knowledge sharers through instructional supervision.

This finding resonates with previous research by Haramain and Sumapal (2023), which similarly highlights the use of a variety of instructional supervision practices of supervisors along the three phases of supervision when supervising their teachers. Similarly, Billones and Sumapal (2019) reveal that instructional supervision practices were conducted and observed by the supervisors. However, supervisors also faced several challenges during their supervisory duties, and most of these hindered the success of supervision and affected the entire school and classroom instructional performance. According to Ngole and Mkulu (2021), supervisors must refine their leadership practices to achieve optimal effectiveness, thereby enhancing the teaching and learning processes of their teachers and students.

Additionally, their study noted that a competent leader possesses the capacity to discern the obstacles encountered by both students and teachers and to seek viable solutions. Thus, to enhance their effectiveness, supervisors must guide, support, and assess their teachers' performance. Additionally, the observed instructional supervision practices can be contextualized through the lens of the Developmental Supervision Theory, which suggests that a collaborative process must occur between a more experienced educator (the supervisor) and a less experienced educator (the supervisee) to enhance the supervisee's professional growth and effectiveness. This theoretical framework explains the three phases of instructional supervision: guidance, support, and performance assessment, which a supervisor must go through to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Teacher's Guidance

Supervisors most often employ guidance in instructional supervision, making it the second most practiced of the three phases of instructional supervision. Based on the Developmental Supervision Theory, this phase of developmental supervision includes helping the teacher set developmental goals, prepare, and plan; sharing best practices and strategies; and mentoring and coaching the teacher to improve and attain his/her professional goals. This implies that supervisors actively facilitate their teachers' professional growth and development. This also suggests that school heads play a crucial role in fostering a supportive and growth-oriented environment where teachers can thrive and continuously enhance their teaching practices. This phase of instructional supervision indicates that supervisors serve as guides and coordinators, mediating between teachers and educational objectives to improve teaching and learning processes.

The study's findings align with previous studies by Basilio (2021), Haramain and Sumapal (2023), and Sunaryo (2020), which found that guidance is the second-most-practiced phase of instructional supervision. Sunaryo (2020) underscores that supervisors aim to improve the teaching and learning process by helping teachers set developmental goals that have a positive, significant effect on changes in teacher performance and professional growth. Basilio (2021) also underscores that regular mon-

itoring and guidance of teachers leads to a more engaging learning environment. Haramanin and Sumapal (2023) emphasize that the supervisors' role in setting instructional goals, providing guidance, and ensuring effective educational strategies are in place is crucial for meeting the needs of diverse learners and promoting good teaching practices.

In addition, supervisors, as highlighted by U-Sayee and Adomako (2021), must provide direct guidance and leadership to ensure teachers align with organizational goals. This is because teachers play a crucial role in achieving educational goals, emphasizing the need for continuous development in professionalism and performance (Wardani et al., 2021). Karim et al. (2021) stress the pivotal role of teacher competencies and principal support in enhancing teacher performance through effective supervision, aligning with the overarching theme's emphasis on supervision. Through supervision, teachers can refine their teaching practices to help students produce high-quality outputs (Hakim et al., 2020).

In this phase, supervisors consistently practice fostering collaboration among teachers, particularly by facilitating Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) or similar structures, during the guidance phase of instructional supervision. This indicator, along with the teachers' guidance phase, got the highest rate. By actively promoting teachers' self-development and supporting these collaborative initiatives, supervisors create an environment conducive to mutual learning and professional growth. Through this approach, supervisors not only enhance teachers' professional development but also cultivate a sense of community and shared purpose within the school, ultimately leading to improved teaching practices and student outcomes. Additionally, the main reason supervisors conduct PLCs is to create a collaborative learning community that enhances student engagement and aligns goals and priorities. This emphasizes the importance of creating a collaborative learning community where educators work together to align goals and priorities to enhance student engagement.

Based on the researcher's data analysis, supervisors consider providing structural support and resources through profes-

sional sharing. This theme encompasses the provision of structural support and resources by school heads to facilitate PLCs. It includes allocating time in the school schedule for PLC meetings.

The finding supports the study by Abbaspour et al. (2024), which revealed that principals play a pivotal role in guiding teachers by promoting their self-development and professional sharing. Antinluoma et al. (2021) note that principals played a major role in advancing schools through professional sharing. The study further explained that professional sharing practices through PLCs were reported to have many positive effects, strengthening instruction, learning, and support. Supervisors' support, human resources, and enabling structures must be secured for it to succeed. According to Sinnayah et al. (2023), PLCs refined their teaching practices and encouraged a collaborative culture that often leads to professional development. This emphasizes that there is a structured agenda set by school heads, focusing on lesson planning, allocation of responsibilities, inclusion of appropriate teaching strategies, and selection of relevant activities, with flexibility to adjust the frequency based on specific needs or circumstances.

Moreover, based on the researcher's data analysis, supervisors consider structural assistance and resources through promoting collaboration. This theme emphasizes that PLCs improve students' learning experience, particularly through the development of high-quality lesson plans and assessments. These emphasize that supervisors encourage a culture of open communication and collaboration within PLCs, where teachers feel comfortable sharing their experiences and supporting one another in addressing common challenges.

Similarly, Printy and Liu (2021) found that guiding teachers by promoting collaboration during PLCs helps improve student learning through collegial interactions and professional support. With the guidance of the supervisors, teachers collaborate to ensure that all students learn at high levels. This practice encompasses peers helping peers. According to Baffour-Awuah (2011), as cited by Kholid and Rohmantika (2019), supervision can improve classroom practices and lead to student success by

enhancing teachers' professional growth and work performance. Additionally, Lin et al. (2018) stress that teachers, guided by supervisors, work with their peers, collect and analyze classroom data, share best practices, and make instructional decisions as a team. As supervisors foster PLCs within the school organization, teachers engage in deeper learning as teaching professionals to better meet their students' needs. Furthermore, Haiyan and Allan (2018) stressed the importance of principal commitment and active involvement in spearheading PLC initiatives, alongside the need for sustained support and monitoring to ensure the longevity of PLCs.

On the other hand, the school supervisors in this study's least practiced indicator under teachers' guidance is assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi to determine strategies that best work in the teaching and learning process, and to outline specific strategies and timelines for achieving their goals. This means that supervisors, on average, are slightly less involved in this indicator than others, and that they give slightly less emphasis or attention to assisting teachers in developing their action plans. This suggests it is not being prioritized or implemented effectively by school supervisors. This could indicate a gap in guidance or a need for improvement in the supervision practices within the educational setting.

While actively engaged in various aspects of instructional supervision, supervisors may need to place greater emphasis on assisting teachers in developing and implementing lesson plans and syllabi. The fact that this indicator is the least practiced among the teachers' guidance phase indicators suggests a potential gap in the guidance supervisors provide to help teachers set and achieve their instructional goals. This shortfall may stem from various factors, such as competing demands on supervisors' time and resources or a lack of awareness of the importance of action planning in driving teacher effectiveness. Addressing this gap requires supervisors to prioritize and invest more effort in collaborating with teachers to develop actionable strategies and timelines for improving teaching and learning outcomes. By doing so, supervisors can better guide teachers in their professional growth journey, ultimately enhancing instructional quality and student achievement within their schools.

Sustainability and follow-through are some of the reasons why supervisors have difficulty assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi. This underscores the complexity of lesson planning and syllabus development in education, emphasizing the need for educators to be adaptable, resourceful, and responsive to the dynamic nature of teaching and learning environments.

Moreover, differing needs and priorities are among the challenges school heads face when assisting teachers in crafting lesson plans and syllabi. This challenge arises because teachers have distinct teaching styles, educational philosophies, and classroom dynamics, leading to differing preferences and approaches in lesson planning. This indicates a struggle to balance administrative responsibilities with the need to support teachers in their professional development and implementation of action plans. Moreover, these statements highlight the difficulty of supervising teachers in crafting lesson plans, given time constraints. The administrator expresses that heavy workloads make it challenging to assist teachers in creating their action plans, particularly when there is a specific format or framework to follow. This finding validates Ampofo et al. (2019), in which school supervisors in Ghana have inadequate supervision of lesson preparation and action plans done by teachers that affect the teacher's role performance. Similarly, a study by Akib and Mushin (2019) emphasizes that supervisors' inadequate time spent supervising teachers in crafting their action plans led to a decline in Nigeria's overall educational system. Additionally, the study by Chiwamba et al. (2022) revealed that heads of schools demonstrated a significant understanding of their supervisory instructional duties but did not effectively engage teachers in improving professional skills, especially in assisting teachers in crafting their action plans. School supervisors should regularly review teachers' lessons and action plans to ensure quality education for learners (Michael, 2019).

Supervisors, most of the time, are highly skilled teachers' support. The high level of support provided by supervisors during instructional supervision in private sectarian secondary schools creates a positive, nurturing environment for teachers. With teachers' support highly practiced by supervisors, it is evi-

dent that supervisors prioritize supporting teachers in their professional development. This implies that teachers in these schools receive consistent and substantial support, fostering a culture of collaboration, growth, and continuous improvement. Such proactive involvement from supervisors can have far-reaching implications, including increased teacher morale, enhanced instructional quality, and, ultimately, improved student outcomes. By recognizing and valuing the importance of teacher support, private sectarian secondary schools are likely to cultivate a more conducive and empowering educational environment, benefiting both educators and students alike.

Based on the researcher's data analysis, supervisors consider cultivating a dynamic learning environment as the reason they prioritize providing support to teachers within the framework of instructional supervision. This theme includes enhancing instructional effectiveness, creating a learning culture, and promoting self-efficacy and autonomy. These themes explain why teachers' support was regarded as the most frequently practiced phase of instructional supervision among private sectarian secondary school supervisors. This collectively highlights a focus on enhancing teachers' capabilities through professional development opportunities such as seminars and workshops. By investing in their teachers' continuous learning and growth, they seek to equip them with the skills and knowledge needed to deliver quality education.

The finding supports the study by David et al. (2021), which highlighted the importance of teachers' support in instructional supervision, where instructional supervision practices of educational supervisors significantly improve teachers' professional competence, making them more effective for the benefit of learners. The learners' attainment is determined by the quality of teaching, which depends on the effectiveness of the instructional supervision provided by the department head teacher and the school principal. It was also highlighted in the study by Ngloe and Mklulu (2020) that effective instructional supervision was found to be the key factor for academic performance in schools, and that instructional supervision should be ongoing, focused on teacher support and learners' needs.

Additionally, in this phase, supervisors always practice listening to and responding to teachers' concerns, making it the indicator with the highest score in this phase. This means supervisors are good at listening to teachers and helping them with their problems. This can make teachers feel more confident and better about themselves when they're teaching. This shows that school supervisors are doing their best to inspire and motivate teachers and are also sharing new ways to teach by talking with them. When they listen to and respond to teachers' concerns, it shows they're there to help and make the school a good place for teaching and learning. Supervisors prioritize recognizing and appreciating the hard work and achievements of teachers, actively acknowledging the valuable contributions they make to the school community.

The finding supports the study of Haramain and Sumapal (2023), which revealed that having a supportive school supervisor can make a significant difference for teachers. When instructional leaders are aware of what is happening in the teaching and learning environment, they are better able and willing to provide the necessary resources and materials that support teachers' instructional efforts. Therefore, the support and responsiveness of school heads to teachers' concerns are crucial for enhancing instructional practices. Similarly, the study by Emanuel and Mwila (2023) revealed that supervision itself increased partnership between teachers and school-based supervisors. Teachers perceive internal supervision as an opportunity for them to discuss teaching and learning challenges. The study found that teachers needed more opportunities for improvement, but this could be achieved if they were actively involved in supervision.

Moreover, the provided finding can be explained by the qualitative data that supervisors listen to and respond to teachers' concerns. Supervisors use the strategy of establishing transparent communication channels to support teachers. This refers to establishing clear and open lines of communication between school supervisors and teachers. This theme emphasizes the importance of creating an environment where information flows freely, feedback is welcome, and concerns are addressed openly and honestly. Transparent communication channels enable

teachers to express their thoughts, share ideas, seek assistance, and provide feedback on various aspects of their professional development and teaching practices. This suggests that the school supervisors prioritize open communication and support for their teachers' well-being and professional growth. Also, it indicates that supervisors value teachers' input and perspectives, creating an environment where teachers feel comfortable expressing their thoughts, ideas, and challenges. They commit to supporting teachers and ensuring that their needs are heard and addressed promptly.

These statements further underscore that the supervisors see themselves not only as professional mentors but also as sources of personal support. This finding validates the study of Haramain and Sumapal (2023), which revealed that secondary school supervisors are good at listening to teachers and helping them with their problems. This can make teachers feel really good about themselves and more confident in their teaching. It's like the principals are trying hard to inspire and encourage teachers by talking to them and trying out new ideas together. When principals listen and respond to teachers, it makes them feel supported and makes the whole school a better place to teach and learn.

In addition, during this phase, supervisors highly practice working closely with teachers to identify areas of their teaching practice that could benefit from improvement. This means that although most of the time they employ this practice in supervising their teachers, not all the time do supervisors work closely with teachers to collaborate and pinpoint areas of their teaching practice that could be enhanced. The school supervisor must work closely with teachers and provide support to help build a professional learning community.

The finding resonates with the study by Ozcan (2020), which revealed that when school supervisors support teachers closely and professionally, they offer constructive criticism of teachers' in-class professional competencies, appreciate teachers' knowledge and competencies, and provide an open channel for communication. Moreover, Haramain and Sumapal (2023) emphasized that integrating teacher support can foster a culture

of professional growth and improvement in schools. It is clear from the findings that monitoring classroom work and assessing the entire teaching and learning process should be a continuous exercise if the objective of enhancing students' learning outcomes and teachers' professional efficiency is to be achieved. (Sule et al., 2018)

On the other hand, supervisors working closely with teachers to identify specific areas of their teaching practice that could benefit from improvement were identified as the lowest indicator along the teachers' support phase. Workload pressures can lead to stress, overwhelm, and difficulty managing one's workload effectively. These pressures can arise from various sources, such as high task volume, tight deadlines, administrative duties, meetings, or productivity expectations. Supervisors attribute this low rating to limited opportunities for them to observe teachers in action. Because they have fewer chances to observe teaching practices directly, supervisors find it challenging to identify and address specific areas where teachers could enhance their effectiveness. This implies that participants are struggling to allocate sufficient time to the important aspects of their roles as educators or supervisors.

Teachers' Performance Assessment

Supervisors regard performance assessment as highly practiced, yet it is the least practiced of the three phases of instructional supervision. This means that private sectarian secondary school supervisors frequently practice assessments to work collaboratively with teachers to set goals, monitor progress, and adjust instructional strategies as needed to enhance teaching effectiveness and student achievement. In this instructional supervision phase, the teacher and supervisor discuss the results and constructive feedback of the class observation. Instructional supervision plays a pivotal role in evaluating and enhancing teachers' effectiveness within educational settings. Through this process, administrators and instructional leaders observe and assess teachers' instructional methods, offering valuable feedback and assistance. The primary objective is to ensure that teachers deliver instruction effectively, align with curriculum standards, and foster student learning. Performance

assessment involves systematically collecting data on various aspects of teaching, including lesson planning, instructional techniques, classroom management, and student involvement. Supervisors employ diverse assessment approaches such as classroom observations, analysis of student work, and teacher self-assessment to gather comprehensive evidence of teachers' performance.

This finding supports the study of Basilio (2021), which revealed that instructional supervision systematically entails evaluating teachers' effectiveness in delivering instruction, meeting curriculum standards, and fostering student learning. According to Maisyaroh et al. (2021), supervisors must conduct comprehensive evaluations by observing classroom instruction, assessing student work, and examining lesson plans to collect evidence of teachers' performance. Moreover, in the performance assessment phase of instructional supervision, the teacher is always invited to a session to discuss strengths, weaknesses, and emergent issues prayerfully after the observation (Basilio, 2021). On the other hand, based on the researcher's data analysis, the performance assessment is considered the least practiced phase of instructional supervision, as it involves careful observation, analysis, and feedback, and is therefore complex and challenging. This phase, which often requires significant time, resources, and expertise, and often faces constraints, has a significant impact on supervisors' ability to carry out instructional supervision effectively.

Among the three phases of instructional supervision, the performance assessment phase is the least practiced. In addition, the supervisors consider resource optimization opportunities as a factor that limits their ability to prioritize and invest in teachers' performance assessment. This theme includes time constraints and high-volume tasks. These explain why the teachers' performance assessment was regarded as the least practiced phase in instructional supervision among private sectarian secondary school supervisors. Also, the findings collectively highlight the challenges supervisors encounter in effectively implementing the performance assessment phase of instructional supervision. This finding resonates with the study by Msuya and Mwila (2023), which found that students' academic achievement

is influenced by supervisory practices such as classroom visits, teacher mentoring, assessing teachers' pedagogical abilities, assisting teachers in creating lesson plans, and other creative teaching methods. However, unfriendly working conditions, including a lack of facilities, funding, and dedicated teachers, make it difficult for school heads to carry out their supervisory duties.

This finding supports the study by Allida et al. (2018), which revealed that the supervisor set the purpose, focus, and method of the observation to be used during the pre-conference. These resolutions provide direction and clarity to the whole process. This stage also helps the supervisor and the teacher to connect and establish a relationship of mutual trust and respect. Pre-conferencing conditions teachers to do their best, thus shielding supervisors from identifying their needs. Also, according to Terra and Berhanu (2019), instructional supervisors were not consistently providing teachers with the necessary support for professional and curriculum development. The study further indicates that, rather than focusing more on academic support, supervisors devoted their time to administrative tasks. Furthermore, in the study conducted by Abera and Ayalew (2020), instructional supervisors encountered various challenges that hindered the effective implementation of supervision. These challenges included difficulties in selecting suitable individuals for supervisory roles, a lack of supervision manuals, insufficient budgets, facilities, and materials, teachers' resistance to supervision due to unawareness of its importance, principals' overwhelming workloads, and inadequate training for supervisors.

In the performance assessment phase of instructional supervision, ensuring that teachers' classroom priorities are consistent with the goals and directions of the school received the highest weighted average. This finding indicates that school supervisors strongly urge teachers to ensure that what they do in their classrooms aligns with the school's overall aims. When teachers align their priorities with the school's goals, they become more effective teachers, ultimately leading to better learning outcomes for students. This further underscores the importance of collaboration and alignment between teachers and the school's broader objectives in fostering student success.

Moreover, the finding can be further explained by the qualitative data, which indicate that optimizing the frequency of classroom observation focuses on verifying that the content taught by teachers aligns with the prescribed curriculum standards. The findings indicate that supervisors need to ensure teachers' performance aligns with established educational standards, thereby contributing to high-quality education and student success. This further underscores that supervisors evaluate how teachers assess student learning to ensure that assessment practices are fair, reliable, and aligned with educational standards. They track educational outcomes to gauge the effectiveness of teachers' instruction in achieving desired learning goals. This implies that supervisors play a crucial role in promoting a culture of continuous improvement among teachers by fostering reflection, collaboration, and professional growth. Supervisors need to assess the effectiveness of teachers' chosen teaching methodologies in facilitating student learning, including observing classroom instruction to determine whether teachers are employing strategies that are appropriate to the subject matter and conducive to student engagement and understanding.

The finding resonates with the studies of Allida et al. (2018), who highlighted the importance of regular classroom observation, a practice frequently conducted by private-sector principals to monitor teachers' adherence to the curriculum, provide feedback, ensure the appropriate use of instructional aids, and follow up on previous instructions. This supervision helps teachers improve punctuality and teaching methods (Amin et al., 2022), aligning with Ubogu (2020) and Mwaniki and Guantai's (2018) assertion that frequent instructional supervision contributes to instructional enhancement and teacher professional development. Moreover, Allida et al. (2018) emphasized the need for regular classroom observation, which they said should not be done only when needed. The study also concluded that there is a need to implement training programs to enhance the practices of principals and teachers in effective, contemporary instructional supervision (Suleiman et al., 2020).

Conversely, pointing out specific strengths in teachers' instructional practices in post-observation feedback received the lowest rating but is still considered highly practiced. Despite its

lower rating, this finding emphasizes that school supervisors still see strengths in how teachers teach, especially when they give feedback after observing classes. This feedback lets principals check how well their advice is working. This feedback aims to help teachers grow, solve problems, and improve their teaching. The results show that supervisors are recognizing teachers' strengths and offering guidance to improve teaching and learning. By addressing any weak points during evaluations, teaching, and learning can get even better. It's important for supervisors to accurately see how well each teacher is doing and have a way to keep improving things regularly.

This finding can be further explained by the qualitative data, which indicate that supervisors also ensure teacher engagement in reflective dialogue, especially during the performance assessment phase of instructional supervision. This refers to teachers and observers reflecting on the teaching methods, student interactions, classroom management strategies, and overall effectiveness in delivering the curriculum. The findings indicate that supervisors offer constructive feedback, share observations, and collaboratively explore solutions to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

The finding supports the study by Guamos and Jalos (2023), which revealed that internal issues such as poor supervisory skills, communication gaps, and rigid rule imposition directly impede effective supervision and potentially contribute to conflicts within the school community. Notably, the absence of essential post-conference after every class observation has a significant impact on teachers' performance, student achievement, and the school community. It is also in consonance with the study of Lyonga (2018), which revealed that supervision practices need to provide immediate feedback and tangible ways to assist a teacher in performing better in the teaching-learning process and in supporting his/her professional development. As such, effective supervision helps teachers improve their work performance, develop the ability and confidence they need in classroom practice, and ensure professional growth and teacher quality. In addition, according to Sumapal and Haramain (2023), supervisors demonstrate dedication to improving teaching practices and fostering professional growth by motivating

teachers to align their goals with those of the school and by acknowledging their strengths through feedback following observations. Through effective supervision and constructive feedback, supervisors can support teachers' ongoing development, resulting in better teaching and learning outcomes across the school.

The quantitative and qualitative findings presented in this study served as the basis for formulating a proposed instructional supervisory plan for school supervisors and key teachers in private sectarian secondary schools. This plan is designed to provide a structured framework for supervising and improving teaching and learning practices within an educational institution. It aims to improve their practices in assessing teachers' performance during instructional supervision.

Limitations and Future Directions

While this research provides useful information, it does have some limitations to consider. First of all, the results might be relevant only to the context of school heads and department heads at private sectarian secondary schools and not transferable to other types of schools. Also, the study examined a narrow group of respondents – just principals with at least 3 years of experience and teachers from private sectarian secondary schools within a single province. This may mean that their experiences don't fully represent the views of all school heads in similar schools. Additionally, because the study relied on teacher feedback validation, it may capture only a limited view of how school leaders supervise their teachers. Finally, it considered only how school heads and department heads supervise, using three established phases, without accounting for personal factors or experiences that could alter their supervision.

The study's limitations, however, open the door to further research. Future work could examine a wider range of school administrators, including heads of public secondary and elementary schools, across a broader geographic scope. It would be valuable to understand supervision practices across a variety of educational settings, from private schools to colleges and universities. Comparative studies might look at supervision techniques used by different administrative groups.

Moreover, additional research could pay closer attention to the factors that shape how leaders supervise teachers, such as individual characteristics and experiences, situational variables, leadership approaches, and the various policies and challenges they face. Understanding which aspects of supervision are most strongly linked to different supervision practices can shed light on what makes supervision most effective. Including input from teachers and other involved parties can provide a fuller picture of supervision and help develop more comprehensive approaches. Finally, while this study examined supervision strategies in detail through a qualitative lens, further quantitative research could assess how common these strategies are for enhancing learning, improving teaching effectiveness, and ensuring timely resource provision in schools. The results presented in this study served as the basis for formulating the proposed instructional supervisory plan for teachers and school heads/ department heads of private sectarian secondary schools. This instructional supervisory plan responds to the growing need for effective instructional supervision in educational settings. It provides a structured framework for guiding, supporting, and assessing teachers' instructional performance, emphasizing the development of their collaborative approaches. It aims to effectively allocate resources, provide targeted support, and implement evidence-based practices to improve instructional quality.

Additionally, an instructional supervisory plan helps establish clear expectations, accountability measures, and professional development opportunities for educators, ultimately fostering a culture of continuous improvement and excellence in teaching. The instructional supervisory plan was subjected to internal validation by the panel members, after which it was externally validated by experts composed of school heads, master teachers, and district supervisors who hold doctorate degrees. Based on their evaluation, the instructional supervisory plan was found highly valid, with a validity rating of 4.93. The validators' comments and suggestions were incorporated into the enhancement training.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated instructional supervision practices at Catholic Schools in the Diocese of La Union, employing a mixed-method approach. Quantitative findings revealed varying degrees of adherence to the instructional supervision phases, with a strong emphasis on teacher support rather than performance assessment. Challenges in executing performance assessments were noted due to their resource-intensive nature. Strategies employed included resource provision, transparent communication, and alignment with educational standards, aimed at enhancing teaching quality and fostering a supportive environment.

School supervisors play a crucial role in instructional supervision, going beyond oversight to nurture a conducive environment for teachers' professional growth. Adopting a constructive approach involving feedback and mentorship can empower educators and improve student outcomes. Emphasizing a dynamic learning environment and resource optimization underscores the essence of instructional supervision, fostering continuous improvement and innovation. The developed Comprehensive Triphasic Model of Instructional Supervision offers insights into improving teaching effectiveness and student learning achievements.

Implications suggest crafting instructional supervisory plans to delineate roles and expectations, and promote coherence and effectiveness. An effective supervisory blueprint involves organized evaluations and joint goal-setting for impactful supervision. Recommendations include implementing the instructional supervision strategy outlined in the study and exploring potential research directions to deepen understanding and refine supervisory practices.

The paper's utilization in Diocesan schools entails disseminating findings and implementing the instructional supervisory plan for both supervisors and teachers. This involves communication with Diocesan schools to facilitate integration, emphasizing the importance of organized evaluation and joint efforts to enhance teaching quality and student outcomes.

This research underscores the ever-evolving nature of educational administration, where adaptability and innovation are key. As schools strive to meet the diverse needs of learners in an increasingly complex world, effective instructional supervision emerges as a cornerstone for driving positive change. By embracing collaborative approaches and leveraging research-based strategies, educational leaders can pave the way for a brighter future in education, one where every student has the opportunity to thrive.

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